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Democratic Governance and Social Welfare for Older Adults in Nigeria's Fourth Republic

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Abstract

In the evolving trajectory of Nigerian democratic government, many older adults are mired in the wake of poor or severe fracture of social welfare services necessary for good living and optimal functioning at a later stage of one's life. This paper examined democratic governance and social welfare services for older adults in Nigeria's fourth republic (that is, 1999 to date). The social contract theory was adopted as the theoretical framework. The study was purely qualitative and relied more on data gathered from secondary sources such as textbooks, Journal articles, internet materials, conference papers, policy documents, and others. The findings revealed that lack of a comprehensive and workable social policy framework for older adults in Nigeria, coupled with the persistent increase in bureaucratic corruption and a flamboyant/expensive political system and democracy, were the underlying factors to this unsavoury development. This has resulted in an increase in poverty level, inequality, and debt profile among Nigerian older adults, as they no longer have confidence in the development potential of democracy. The paper therefore recommended, amongst other things, the urgent need to review the national constitution and articulate a workable social policy framework for older adults in both formal and informal sectors of the Nigerian economy, declare an emergency on the war against corruption in public institutions and trim down the cost of governance.

Key Words: Democracy, Fourth Republic, Governance, Older Adult, Social Welfare.

Introduction

The essence of democratic government in a nation lies in its ability to ensure the wellbeing of its citizens of all ages (protecting lives and property and providing adequate social welfare services). This could be the only way to measure the government's developmental interest of the people, as its legitimacy derives from the authority invested in it by the people (Bakare, 2013). In some cases, these expectations only amount to mere wishful thinking, especially in developing countries, including Nigeria, where a large percentage of the population is consistently ravaged by poverty, food insecurity, ill-health, and inadequate social welfare services (Olaleye, 2011; Akintayo-Usman & Usman, 2021). The older adults in the population are not exempted from this catastrophe.

In African traditional society, social welfare services for older adults were provided by members of the extended family system, which offered various type of socio-economic insurance and emotional support to stressed members, especially in advanced age. According to Mbah et al. (2017), it was a caring, communal system in which everyone served as his or her brother's/sister's keeper to ensure that no member was deprived of the necessities of life. However, with the emergence of state and urban centres and the increase in population, this traditional system of welfare was destabilised or weakened, leaving older persons vulnerable to the deprivation of essential services (Eboesomi, 2025). This is happening as the population of older persons in most countries is growing. The recent report released by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2024) shows that approximately 9.3 million Nigerians are aged 60 years and above. This number is considered high compared to other African countries, as the provision of satisfactory social services to this group do not commensurate with the increasing population. The pension system which was inherited from the British colonial administration (although with some modifications) to provide financial security for the senior citizens has been largely ineffective to address the welfare challenges of older adults generally as it was only designed to cater for a small group who had opportunity to work in the

formal sector neglecting those who served in the informal sector of the economy (Folorunsho, 2025).

Consequent to the enthronement of democratic governance in 1999, which marked the beginning of Nigeria's fourth Republic and the ousting of military dictatorship, the government initiated a series of programmes and policies that are yet to be fully implemented as part of its commitments to the welfare of older adults. Some of these programmes/policies include; the Senior citizens Act of 2011 enacted by the National Assembly, the National citizens Centre Act 2017/2018, the 2020 National Policy on Ageing, the older persons (rights and privileges) Bill 2025 and the Renewed Hope Initiatives (RHI) initiated by the wife of the current Nigerian president, Senator Oluremi Tinubu (Onogu, 2025). These beautiful programmes, which were targeted at mitigating the challenges of older adults and improving their quality of life, are yet to be implemented in reality. Ogbonna (2017) noted that the social welfare system in Nigeria, from independence periods onward, attracted little attention and funding from the government, thereby posing a threat to those who need the services or cannot access relief from other sources.

In many developed countries, such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, China, Germany and others, social welfare schemes for older people are given appropriate attention with regular payment of retirement benefits and other allowances in addition to a functional health insurance scheme and other programmes targeted at promoting the living standards of older adults (OECD, 2017). This is quite different from what we have in Nigeria and other African countries. Sobowale (2025) argues that for any government to be classified as people-oriented, it must, above all, prioritise the care, liberty, and wellbeing of its members, which must be consistent with the structure and order of the state. Ifunanya (2014) opines that in many states in Nigeria, retired civil servants are owed several months of pension arrears, and sometimes the payment arrives very late, with series of deductions. One implication of this situation is that many of these older persons will continue to live in penury amid dwindling financial

resources, increased health challenges, and the geometric rise in medical bills (Tanyi et al., 2018).

In some cases, the government may claim to be up and doing in fulfilling its mandate to enhance the wellbeing of all segments of the population, including older adults. However, the situation on the ground negates the assertion in many quarters. In addition to the lack of a comprehensive document on older people's welfare, the high level of corruption, and the neglect of social welfare matters by political leaders, the Nigerian democratic governance seems to be more expensive than in other countries (Bakare, 2013).

Based on the foregoing, the study examined democratic governance and social welfare for older adults in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. Specifically, the study sought to determine whether the lack of a workable and comprehensive social welfare policy for older adults was responsible for the ineffectiveness. The study also aims to examine the relationship between bureaucratic corruption and the ineffectiveness of social welfare service provision for older adults. Finally, the study sought to determine whether the expensive political system and democracy have any influence on the government's inability to provide adequate social welfare services for older adults in Nigeria. Previous studies focused more on the pension system and poverty among older adults/retirees in Nigeria and other countries (Gasparini et al., 2007; Ubhenin, 2012). This study aims to fill this knowledge gap.

Literature Review

The government's ability to effectively mitigate the challenges faced by its citizens is one of the underlying reasons for democracy and political leadership. In other words, the developmental potential of any administration is assessed by its ability to provide the necessary social welfare services such as food, financial aid, affordable health facilities, recreational centres, good roads and other facilities geared toward improved quality of life. The literature related to this paper was reviewed under the following sub-headings: Conceptual Clarifications, main discourse which includes; non-existence of a comprehensive

policy on social welfare for older adults, bureaucratic corruption and an expensive political system.

Conceptual Clarifications

Democracy

The term democracy, which has its origin in the Greek city-state, means ‘demos cratos’, which translates to ‘power of the people’. In other words, it shows that power originates from the people. This implies that its legitimacy is derived from the authority invested in it by the people hence, it has to carry the masses along all the time in order to retain its legitimacy (Bakare, 2013). Ideally, democratic government everywhere is expected to guarantee the rights and privileges of the masses. The principles of democratic governance are antithetical to military dictatorship, autocracy, fascism, totalitarianism, or any other form of governance that does not carry the people along in decision-making (Uchegbu, 2016). Since 1999, when Nigeria’s fourth republic commenced, democratic practice in government has not been fully consolidated, especially in matters related to human well-being and social welfare services for the people (Saliu & Ifejika, 2016). Instead of operating within the tenets of democracy, it appears that what has been in place in Nigeria is kleptocracy, which uses military tactics and civilian pretence to govern the country in line with the selfish desires of the leaders. The result is suffering, inequality, underdevelopment, insecurity, corruption, economic collapse, and inflation. Nigerian older adults have been victims of these circumstances, which highlight the urgent need for renewed hope and commitment to democratic principles.

Social Welfare

Social welfare involves the provision of composite and comprehensive integrated services for the vulnerable segment of society, including older adults, children, women and the physically challenged persons. According to Barker (2003), it refers to the system of programmes, benefits and services undertaken by the government to help the population meet their fundamental social, economic, educational and health needs, which are fundamental to the maintenance of society.

According to Zastrow (2013), these services are structured to offer some form of mutual aid to members of society, thereby improving their quality of life. This may also take the form of providing material goods, financial assistance, or health care services to people who are unable to obtain them themselves (Abonyi, 2024). For Oduaran (1996), it is an organized system of programmes aimed at maintaining the economic conditions, health or interpersonal competencies of the population. In addition to providing a kind of safety-net for individuals confronted with such challenges as financial hardship, food insecurity, inaccessibility of healthcare services, terminal diseases and other situations capable of hindering them from attaining better life, social welfare services help the people to bridge the gap in the socio-economic ladder ensuring that everyone has access to opportunities and resources required for a dignified life (Saharan, 2014).

Traditionally, older adults in Nigeria and other African countries relied more on support from children and members of the extended family, although modernization and current social change have disrupted the efficacy of these conventional social support systems (Byaruhanga & Debesay, 2021). The Nigerian government since the onset of the fourth republic with Olusegun Obasanjo as the president to the present administration of Ahmed Bola Tinubu had initiated many policies such as Maintenance and Welfare of Senior Citizens Act (2011), National Senior Citizens Centre Act (2017/2018), National Policy on Ageing (2020), Social Rights and Civic Rights of Older Adult Bill (2025), Renewed Hope Initiatives (2025) and others in addition to the existing pension system, all focused on the special needs of older persons. This implies that the desire to promote the well-being of older persons is part of the national constitution and philosophy of democratic governance. However, the reality on the ground is yet to be seen. Retirees are owed several months of pension benefits and gratuity. The soaring cost of medical services, food crisis, insurgency and banditry, economic collapse, and the high cost of transportation, amongst others, have, in all, been a mockery of an ideal democracy (Oke, 2010). Aminu (2019) also noted that the low pension income of Nigerian senior citizens has

created a socio-economic distance between ordinary people and political office holders. This money is so shameful and meaningless that it can hardly sustain an individual for one week, let alone one month or thereabout.

Older Adult

Old age is a natural process that results in the deterioration of an individual's physical and psychological state over time. The term "older adult" refers to people aged 60 and above. The increasing population of older persons worldwide in the 21st century has prompted a call for adequate social welfare services for older adults, as enshrined in the 1948 United Nations Charter (Byaruhanga & Debesay, 2021). Eke et al (2024) noted that social welfare provision is a significant determinant of wellbeing among older adults, influencing both the physical, psychological and social aspects of their lives.

Main Discourse

Non-existence of comprehensive and workable social policy framework for older adults.

Right from the beginning of the fourth republic in 1999 to date, there has been a lack of a comprehensive, workable social policy designed solely for older adults in Nigeria. Although several policies for older adults were initiated, such as the National Policy on Ageing, the Maintenance and Welfare of Senior Citizens Act, the National Senior Citizens Centre Act, Renewed Hope Initiatives, and others, most of the documents show grave inconsistencies and fragmentation that the court cannot enforce. (WHO, 2018). Eboesemi (2025) noted that, despite many of these policies being well-designed and signed into law, there remains a wide gap between intent and actual practice or implementation. Research evidence has also shown that for many years now, it is only Lagos and Ekiti states that have practically gone into providing social welfare schemes for older adults and equally grant

them waivers in certain public services such as transportation and hospitals since 2018 (Isa, 2025).

Persistent increase in Bureaucratic corruption

Similarly, the high level of corruption among government officials and critical stakeholders in public institutions appears to have exacerbated the lack of, or the ineffectiveness of, social welfare services for older adults in Nigeria. According to Bakare (2013), Nigerians have become accustomed to ugly things to the point that one no longer gets startled upon hearing that billions or millions of naira have been stolen from government coffers. Ikpefan (2025) remarks that while the Nigerian political elites are busy enjoying their jumbo salaries and other allowances that run into millions of naira, many retirees are still receiving N30,000 per month in pensions, while the payment of gratuity has become a mirage. In any society where democracy and governance are conducted transparently, social welfare services for all segments of the population should form part of the administration's service orientation, which is also necessary for societal transformation and the promotion of people's living conditions (Umar & Tafida, 2015). The authors argued that the Nigerian government is yet to have a well-articulated social welfare programme for older adults and other vulnerable groups that is devoid of corrupt practices.

Flamboyant and expensive political system and democracy.

Finally, the government's running costs in Nigeria have been a matter of concern, affecting the efficient delivery of social welfare services to older adults. Imhonopi and Urim (2012) argued that the cost of running democracy in Nigeria and the remuneration of political office holders have become so high, at the expense of the majority of the Nigerian masses, who are trapped in poverty. According to the authors, the salaries of Nigerian federal legislators, which range from N36 million for senators to more than N20 million for House of Representatives members, create a severe imbalance in the socio-economic well-being of the citizens who voted them into power. Ololade (2025) clearly stated that profligate spending has become the bane of democratic

governance failure in Nigeria in the provision of social welfare services to the vulnerable. Nigerian legislators, especially those in the Senate and House of Representatives, also seem to be the highest paid among legislators all over the world (Rabba & Abdulkadir, 2025). More than a decade now, the current Emir of Kano and the former governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria, Sanusi Lamido Sanusi, once reported that about 25% of Nigerian budgetary allocation each year is earmarked for National Assembly expenditure, which is outrageous and greater than 0.2% spent by the entire United States Congress in a year (Ajayi, 2012). Similarly, Nigerian politicians always arrive in a fleet of expensive cars, sirens blaring, while attending official functions, which tend to provoke anger and irritation among the hungry masses who watch them parade with national resources that could have been used to promote a good standard of living for all. This extravagant spending among politicians is also evident in the chain of appointments of ministers, commissioners, Ambassadors, Board members, special assistants, senior special assistants, executive assistants, and others whose jobs cannot be clearly defined. Eriye (2025) noted that this criminal act of diverting communal resources has become an existential issue, undermining the provision of social welfare services for older adults in Nigeria since the emergence of the fourth republic in the democratic experiment.

Theoretical Framework

Social Contract Theory by Jean-Jacques Rousseau in 1762

Many theoretical explanations abound to conceptualise the issues related to democratic governance and social welfare services for older adults. However, for this work, the Social Contract theory propounded by the Geneva philosopher Jean-Jacques Rousseau in 1762 seems more appropriate. The theory, which influenced other Enlightenment philosophers such as Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, and others, focused on the implicit agreement to grant the state the authority to promote freedom, happiness, equality, and the provision of necessary social services for a good life (Tanyi et al., 2018). In other words, the general

will of the people is transferred to the government, which exercises sovereign political power and ensures the well-being of citizens (Saharen, 2014). The enthronement of democratic governance in many countries, including Nigeria, has witnessed a different step in tackling these responsibilities. Many issues bordering on older adults' welfare are being handled with levity by the government. According to Oyedele (2019), pensioners are being owed several months of their pension entitlements and gratuity, leading to many of them living below the poverty line with food insecurity, poor medical services and a dilapidated housing system, which makes them lose hope entirely for the future. Similarly, since only very few of the older adults who served in the formal sector were covered by health insurance, the majority of those who worked in the informal sector or private businesses had to pay out of pocket for health care (Akintayo-USman & Usman, 2021). The situation is more difficult among older adults residing in rural communities (Folorunsho, 2025).

The consequences of the government's breach of contractual rules for providing sustainable social welfare services to its segment of the population threaten the essence of governance and reveal structural lapses in Nigerian democratic governance (Olanrewaju, 2011). This is also an abridgement to Section 14 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which made it clear that the security and welfare of the people (adequate shelter, sustainable and adequate food, reasonable/minimum living wage, old age care, good health facilities and so on) shall be the primary purpose of the government (Mbah, 2014). The relevance of democratic governance, therefore, lies in the care and benefits enjoyed by citizens from the government, which make life easier for people and help them realise their potential.

Methodology

The study aimed to examine the democratic governance and social welfare services for older adults in Nigeria's fourth republic. The study was purely qualitative and relied more on the secondary sources of data. In other words, information was sourced from textbooks, Journal articles, Internet materials, dissertations, government documents or

policy reports, conference proceedings, as well as library materials relevant to the subject under study. The data were reviewed and vetted to ensure appropriateness and consistency with the study objectives, and to prevent the repetition of facts. Content analysis was employed in the analysis of the generated data.

Findings

The study's findings were presented based on qualitative data analysis. These findings were presented in line with the study objectives. One of the findings from the literature search and other documentary evidence is the lack of a comprehensive and workable social policy framework for older persons in most Nigerian states. Mobolaji (2024) opines that, despite the federal government's efforts to articulate an acceptable national policy for older adults in Nigeria for many years now, there is still little to show that the document's contents and evidence align with the aspirations and yearnings of Nigerian older adults. It can therefore be captured from the above finding that the non-existence of a workable social policy for older adults in Nigeria may have been one of the reasons why the majority of this segment of the population are vulnerable to poverty and diseases. Adisa (2019) reports that about 70% of older adults lack the necessary social welfare services, which obviously subject them to poverty and inability to attend to their daily financial, nutritional and health care needs.

The study also found that the increasing rate of corruption among those in charge of public institutions and governance had been a formidable obstacle to adequate social welfare service provision for older adults in Nigeria. Idigo (2024) opines that corruption has become a systemic practice that has engendered a low level of transparency and accountability among actors in Nigerian public institutions and governance. This cankerworm has also been identified as a cause of developmental failures in Nigeria. It is the responsibility of the government to ensure that Nigerian older adults are provided with adequate social welfare services and an improved standard of living, with a sense of honesty and love. In other words, the situation in Nigeria has escalated to the extent that the Independent Corrupt

Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC), the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and other anti-graft agencies can no longer bring it to an end. This ugly situation has become the norm in Nigerian public institutions. Saliu and Ifejika (2016) argued that corruption in Nigeria has submerged a large percentage of the population into abject poverty, while a few feeds fat on the nation's enormous resources. Finally, the findings of the study reveal that jumbo salaries enjoyed by political office holders in Nigeria and irrational spending on government operations have been among the reasons for the government's inability to effectively address the social welfare needs of older adults. Imhonopi and Urim (2012) argued that the cost of running democracy in Nigeria and remuneration of political office holders has become so high compared to other African countries, at the expense of the majority of the Nigerian masses, who are wallowing in hunger.

Discussion

The paper examined democratic governance and social welfare services for older adults in Nigeria's fourth republic. The paper used the social contract theory propounded by Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Hobbes, Locke and others as the theoretical framework. The tenets of this theory hold that the right to protection of life and the provision of adequate social services/good living standards for citizens are the responsibilities of the government and its agencies. This also represents a kind of mutual agreement/social contract. In this respect, the individual's expectations/desires and obligations to the government are well spelt out. In contrast, the government plays a pivotal role in meeting citizens' needs due to its monopolistic control over society's resources (Olanrewaju, 2011).

In many cases, the government do not show the will to fulfil this mutual agreement. This tends to make the provision of social welfare services to citizens, especially older adults, a mirage in Nigeria (Aina et al., 2023). Oyedele (2019) emphasised that the extent to which the well-being of citizens is addressed in a nation depends mainly on the class and nature of those in charge of governance. It is also the duty of the

government to create an enabling environment for citizens to thrive and realise their treasuries, as part of fulfilling its own part of the agreement (Nyabeze & Chikoko, 2021).

Based on the literature reviewed, the paper established that there is lack of a comprehensive and workable social welfare policy framework for older adults in Nigeria. This finding aligns with the argument raised by Tanyi et al. (2018) that social welfare policy documents do not cover the majority of older adults in Nigeria, and that the government's interest lies in advocating for youth employment that has remained unrealistic for decades. The study's findings further established that the persistent rise in bureaucratic corruption in Nigeria has undermined the government's provision of welfare services for older adults under the Fourth Republic. This finding corroborates the submission of Saliu and Ifejika (2016) that bureaucratic corruption has resulted in massive theft of public funds and resources that would have been used to provide social welfare services to citizens. Okwueze (2002) also noted that Nigerian society has, since the attainment of political independence, been submerged by the zeal for material acquisition, resorting to any means to amass wealth regardless of the hardships that citizens may be going through.

Finally, the study's findings show that the current flamboyant and expensive political system and democracy in Nigeria have contributed significantly to the derailment of adequate social welfare service provision for older adults since the onset of democratic governance in 1999. This finding is in tandem with the view of Rabba and Abdulkadir (2022), who argued that Nigerian democracy has become highly expensive and a burden to the citizens, such that the vast amount of money spent on salaries and allowances of political office holders could be used in providing social welfare services for older members of the society and others. Akubo (2025) also noted that, despite trillions of naira accruing from the removal of fuel subsidies, the federal government had not prioritised the provision of efficient social welfare services for older adults and other segments of the population; instead, the leadership continued to lavish funds on unrealistic projects. The

author also noted that the government's interests lie in collecting more loans and sharing them among themselves, as well as expanding the executive's retinue of aides. The political class has also resorted to asking citizens to exercise patience in the provision of social welfare services, which, according to Adekaiyaoja (2024), shows that Nigerian democratic governance is out of touch with the reality of older adults' well-being.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the paper has examined democratic governance in Nigeria and social welfare services for older adults following the onset of the fourth republic in 1999. Findings that emerged from the study shows that the lack of a workable and comprehensive social welfare policy framework for older adults, persistent increase in bureaucratic corruption among stakeholders and people entrusted with the business of governance, and the sustaining of expensive democratic and political systems were instrumental to the ineffective provision of social welfare services for older adults in Nigeria's fourth republic. Many of the Nigerian older adults currently live in debt and abject poverty. They cannot afford their daily meals, as decaying health facilities, poor housing, exorbitant transportation fares, and other problems persist, while the political class live in affluence and admonish the masses to exercise patience.

Recommendations

Based on the above conclusion, the following recommendations were advanced:

- There is a need to review the Nigerian constitution or replace it entirely with a new one that incorporates details of old-age policies and social welfare services for older adults, rather than the fragmented documents currently in use. The policies will cover older adults in both formal and informal sectors.
- Cash transfer programme through the individual's mobile should be given to older adults in rural areas who are not

covered by a pension and national health insurance. In contrast, the amounts paid as pensions should be scaled up in line with the economic realities.

- There is also the need to declare an emergency in the war against corruption, close all forms of corruption-related leakages in public institutions, and mete out appropriate punishment to the culprit, irrespective of the person's status or social position.
- Finally, there is the need to trim down the cost of governance, as extravagant spending by political officeholders tends to reflect a growing disconnect between economic hardship and poor social welfare services, which seems to have marred the lives of Nigerian older adults in the 21st century.

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